

Indian Gums as Emulsifying Agents

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Of the four Indian gums studied, the two, namely, gum khair and gum ghatti, produce very stable emulsions, suitable for use in industry. The stability of stabilised emulsions of these two gums is appreciably greater at all pHs. Gum karaya, although inferior, may be used as a stabiliser, especially in the preparation of viscous emulsions. Of the four gums, neem is the worst; it deteriorates rapidly on keeping, its emulsion is much coarse with respect to other gum emulsions.

In recent years substantial advance has been made in the knowledge of the chemistry of the gums, particularly those of industrial importance. A good account of the work in this field has been outlined by Mantell⁴ and also by Norman⁵. Yet much remains to be done in chemical field, particularly with regard to the less-common gums.

Most of the study lately undertaken is on the measurement of viscosity and interfacial tension with varying pH of gum tragacanth and gum acacia. Investigations were also carried out by Krantz and Gordon² on the use of acacia and tragacanth, with particular reference to the effect of the hydrogen-ion concentration of the aqueous phase. Agreement with the results of Krantz and Gordon was obtained by Lotzker and Maclay³ who compared pectin, gum tragacanth, gum karaya, and gum acacia as emulsifying agents for olive oil, cotton seed oil, and mineral oil, respectively, in water. They found gum karaya to be equal to pectin as an emulsifying agent. Little or no work has been done on the emulsifying capabilities of the Indian gums. In the present work it is intended to study the efficiency of the following four selected Indian gums in the preparation of stable emulsions with respect to hydrogen-ion concentration:

(a) Gum Karaya (*Sterculia urens*), a substitute for tragacanth and cheaper than tragacanth.

(b) Khair gum (*Acacia catechu*), the source of cutch, an important tanning extract found in most parts of India.

(c) "Gum Neem", *Melica indica* (syn: *Azadirachta indica*).

(d) Gum Ghatti, derived from *Anogeissus latifolia*.

1. *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, **58**, 243.

2. *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1926, **15**, 93; 1930, **19**, 1181.

3. *Ind Eng. Chem.*, 1943, **35**, 1294.

4. "The Water Soluble Gums", Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1947.

5. "The Biochemistry of Cellulose, the Polyuronides, Lingnin, etc.", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1937.

EXPERIMENTAL

Good and clear crystals of these samples* were selected and powdered in a mortar. The powdered gums were then passed through a sieve of 0.05-0.075 mm mesh size to obtain fine grains. These were dispersed in water by allowing them to swell for about 24 hr. The entire mass was then heated to about 40°.

The emulsions were prepared by the Continental method to contain 40% kerosene oil. The size-frequency analysis was done immediately and at different intervals of time by the method of King and Mukerjee¹. The change of specific surface was plotted against time as abscissa for several emulsions to illustrate the agreement between the data on the change of specific surface with time and the exponential hypothesis. The lines were determined by fitting the data to the equation:

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dc} = K' \sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient, and K = stability coefficient) by the method of least squares. The curves representing the degradation of the emulsions are all linear; hence a measure of the slope provides a quantitative comparison of stability. Accordingly, the slope of each curve had been measured and divided by the graphically determined initial interface (σ_0) to furnish the rate of decrease per unit area of interface. This is termed the instability factor and might be defined as the decrease of each cm² of fresh emulsion per day. The reciprocal of this would be a direct measure of emulsion stability (K).

TABLE I
Data for 40% kerosene oil emulsions.

Emulsion No.	Wt. of stabiliser.	pH of diluent.	Graphically determined initial specific area (σ_0).	Stability coeff. $K \times 10^3$.
A. Gum Karaya-stabilised emulsions.				
89	1.0 g.	3	12.68 cm ² /g.	40.22
90	1.0	6	10.99	44.07
91	1.0	9	10.26	38.28
B. Gum Khair-stabilised emulsions.				
92	1.0	3	13.43	78.57
93	1.0	6	13.71	111.65
94	1.0	9	12.65	106.06
C. Gum Ghattay-stabilised emulsions.				
95	1.0	3	13.87	138.94
96	1.0	6	13.71	142.37
97	1.0	9	13.03	110.94
D. Gum Neem-stabilised emulsions.				
98	1.0	3	6.43	11.59
99	1.0	6	12.16	10.02
100	1.0	9	5.34	6.37

*The forest utilisation officer, Maharashtra State, Poona, was kind enough to supply the samples of Indian gums.

Gum Karaya.—The suspension of gum karaya (so-called Indian tragacanth) shows high viscosity and the interfacial tension is pretty high. The values are definitely greater than those observed with gum tragacanth. Size-frequency analysis on 1.0% gum-stabilised emulsions reveals that the dispersions of globules are generally coarse compared to soap-stabilised emulsions of King and Mukerjee¹, the particle size ranging between 5 and 10 μ . At pH 6 and 9, a fair percentage of globule sizes of 15 μ , however, is visible. The initial area is fairly high, but the stability factor ranges between 44 and 38, as may be seen from Table I. The emulsions are definitely more stable than the corresponding tragacanth ones, studied previously. This is apparently due to high internal viscosity of the emulsion which prevents coalescence of the particles into bigger ones.

Gum Khair.—The suspension is slightly more viscous than that of gum acacia and causes an appreciable lowering of interfacial tension. The dispersions are once again coarse at all pHs, ranging from 3 to 9. The particles were of 5-10 μ on the first day, and remained so even after 2 months with a slight change in percentages. Initial specific areas are fairly high. The stability factors are also high in the range of 6 to 9 pH, ranging from 111.65 to 106.06. The stability is reduced to 78.57 when the pH value is definitely acidic, namely pH 3.

Gum Ghatti.—Like gum khair, the suspensions are slightly viscous and cause greater lowering of interfacial tension. At all pHs, the globule-size distributions are once again coarse. Variation of particle size is similar to gum khair-stabilised emulsions. The initial specific area is high at all pHs. It is very stable at all pHs. The stability at pH 3 and 6 is as high as 138.94 and 142.37, whereas it is lowered to 110.94 at pH 9.

Gum Neem.—The suspensions of gum neem are less viscous, but show a great lowering of interfacial tension. In the beginning, particles of 5-15 μ were present, but within 2 weeks of storage, particles up to 30 μ were visible. Thus it is concluded from the globule-size distribution that the emulsion deteriorates rapidly on aging. The initial specific areas are also comparatively low and so is the stability factor (Table I.). As the emulsion is coarse and deteriorates rapidly, its use for preparation of stable emulsions cannot be recommended.

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